

Appendix 1:

A: Research Terms

The search was done using the Boolean operator in different data sets as follows:

(Migrants OR workers OR “immigrants’ workers”) AND (labor OR “workforce” OR “labor law” OR “occupational safety”) AND (Qatar)

We searched the following databases, and we retrieved the following number of papers in each dataset.

Search in	Return value
PubMed	52
ScienceDirect	65
Google Scholar	100
Total	217

B: Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Population: Immigrants, Workers, Labor, Work-related injuries, workforce
- Intervention: Qatar,
- Study Design: the focus will be on empirical studies (Quantitative and Qualitative)
- Type of publication: peer-reviewed articles, thesis, and reports
- Year of publication: 2018 until now
- Language of publication: English only.

Exclusion Criteria

- Population: Non-Immigrants, All types of workers rather than labor workforce.
- Intervention: All countries except Qatar
- Type of publication: Reviews, proposals, survey-based studies.
- Year of publication: All studies before 2018
- Language of Publication: Any studies used rather than the English language.